

CHICKPEA IS THE MEDICINE OF HEALTH

Z.Bobokulov

Samarkand branch of TDAU, associate professor, PhD

J.Tukhtamishova

bachelor student of Samarkand branch TDAU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7807656>

Abstract. In this article reviewed detailed chickpeas one of the Legumes which has a botanical description, chemical composition, and medicinal properties, as well as its effects and use on the human body.

Keywords: Chickpea, protein, vitamin, amino acid, medicinal, human organism.

Chickpea is one of the leguminous grain crops, and it is an annual plant widely used in field farming in Uzbekistan. The stem grows strong, and branchy, and does not lie down. The leaves are dark downy, the flowers are usually white or reddish purple, and the pods are short, convex, containing 1-3 grains [1,2,3,4,5].

Chickpeas are often used in the preparation of various dishes, especially in soups and pilaf. Grains are boiled and cooked separately with meat. It is also eaten as a fried cereal. White grain varieties are used for food, and black grain varieties are used for fodder.

Chickpeas contain up to 20-30% protein, including up to 8.3% non-essential amino acids (valine, isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine, threonine, tryptophan) and up to 13.62% essential amino acids, as well as 4.32% lipids, contains 3% sugars, starch, 43.5% starch, and 3% pectin. Chickpeas contain a large number of vitamins, including carotene, group B vitamins, and vitamin E. Chickpeas are very rich in macro and microelements. It contains a large amount of potassium, calcium, silicon, magnesium, sulfur, phosphorus, aluminum, chalk, iron, molybdenum, selenium, and zinc. In terms of the content of selenium, chickpeas rank first among all legumes.

The use of chickpeas as a medicine is known in the literature. Chickpeas are also used to treat some pains by heating them. Raw and boiled chickpea seeds have been used to treat intestinal and diarrheal diseases. In France, the effect of chickpeas on urinary organs has been studied. It has been found that it has a good effect on the retention of urine and relieves the pain and colic that occurs during its separation. Malic, citric and sorbic acids extracted from the pods and leaves of the pea plant are used for this purpose. Therefore, among the grain-leguminous crops, chickpeas are grown more medicinally in the countries of Southeast Asia, India, China and Burma.

In folk medicine, raw and boiled chickpea pods, as well as decoction made from chickpea grass and skin, are used as a diuretic in kidney-stone disease. In the folk medicine of Tajikistan, fried peas are recommended to prevent constipation and restore the work of the digestive organs.

Buqrot, one of the ancient judges, also mentioned that chickpeas are good food for a person and have a diuretic and arousal effect. According to Ibn Sina, chickpeas are white, red and black. Black peas have a stronger effect. Chickpea decoction is useful for diarrhea and jaundice, opens blocked channels in the liver and spleen. Black chickpea decoction combined

with mineral oil, wild turnip oil and parsley can break up bladder and kidney stones. When a decoction of chickpeas is drunk for dinner, a person will feel better and his voice will be clearer. When a chickpea decoction is drunk or crushed and applied to the appropriate areas of the body, it removes blood clots, improves a person's complexion, and helps to relieve toothache. Chickpea oil is a cure for iron deficiency, and chickpea flour is a cure for malignant growths, cancer, and scabies.

Chickpeas cleanse the blood, increase appetite, and benefit the lungs. Chickpeas stop bleeding, diarrhea, cough, shortness of breath, treat hemorrhoids, and remove stones formed in the seminal vesicles.

In modern medicine, it has been found that the proteins contained in chickpeas are very close to animal proteins. Selenium, which is present in a considerable amount (about 28.5 μg %) in chickpeas, has antioxidant properties and prevents some types of malignant tumors. However, in some people, chickpeas relax the stomach and cause constipation. Adding dill or cumin to chickpeas can help reverse the negative effects of chickpeas on the digestive system. In short, the chickpea plant has a positive effect on the human body with its energy and nutrition, and is widely used in the prevention and treatment of many diseases.

References:

- 1.Хамдамов И., Бобомурадов З., Сувонова Г., Джумаев М. Нўхат: ҳам озуқа, ҳам дори. //Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги. 2009. № 3. 18-б.
- 2.Fayzimurodov, J., & Toshmurodov, E. (2023). BEDA O 'SIMLIGINING CHORVACHILIKKA VA TUPROQ UNUMDORLIGIGA FOYDALI XUSUSIYATLARI. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(4), 76-78.
- 3.Bobokulov, Z. R., & Bobomurodov, Z. S. (2021). Productivity of chickpea varieties and the effect of different planting times and depths on grain quality indicators. NVEO-NATURAL VOLATILES & ESSENTIAL OILS Journal| NVEO, 7524-7532.
- 4.Bobokulov, Z., & Botirov, A. (2022). Teaching agricultural sciences: essence and teaching technology. Jilin Daxue Xuebao (Gongxueban). Journal of Jilin University (Engineering and Technology Edition), 42(03), 12-17.
- 5.Qahhorov, S. Q. S., Sanayev, S. T., & Botirov, A. E. (2022). BROKKOLI KARAMINING OZIQT OVQAT HAVSIZLIGIDA TUTGAN O'RNI. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(4), 97-101.

